

Tensor-FLAMINGO: Tensor-based Fast Low-rank Matrix completion algorithm for reconstructing high-resolution 3D Genome Organizations

Summary

Tensor-FLAMINGO aims to accurately reconstruct the 3D chromatin structures for every single cell from super sparse scHi-C contact maps (missing rate > 99.95%). Remarkably, the tensor-completion-based method borrows information across single cells, while preserving the unique structural variations across single cells.

Introduction

Tensor-FLAMINGO takes scHi-C data of tens to hundreds of single cells as inputs and reconstructs the single-cell 3D chromatin structures. Tensor-FLAMINGO has two major steps. In the first step, the contact maps of all single cells are modeled as a sparse tensor and then completed using the low-rank tensor completion method. This step gives a dense tensor and imputes the missing values of the original scHi-C data. In the second step, the 3D genome structures are reconstructed for each single cell from the completed chromatin contact map using [FLAMINGO](#).

Dependencies

The implementation of the algorithm is based on but not necessarily restricted to python/3.11.5 and R/4.3.3

R packages

GenomeInfoDb and prodlim, mgcv, progress if not already installed based on the R version used.

```
if (!require("BiocManager", quietly = TRUE))
  install.packages("BiocManager")
```

```
BiocManager::install("GenomeInfoDb")
```

```
install.packages("prodlim")
install.packages("mgcv")
install.packages("progress")
```

python packages

pyfftw, scipy, numpy, pandas, joblib and ray.

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

Tip: users may choose not to specify the package version when installing.

`run.sh` provides an example to run on SLURM job scheduler.

Output data format

For each single cell, a data frame with four columns containing the fragment id (the first column) and the 3D coordinates (the other three columns) will be generated and stored in "OUTPUTS_FOLDER/Tensor-FLAMINGO_results"

Visualize the 3D genome structure using ParaView

Similar to FLAMINGO, Tensor-FLAMINGO predictions can also be visualized using ParaView. To visualize the 3D genome structure using FLAMINGO, the user need to convert the 3D coordinates into a `.vtk` file. In the `tFlamingorLite` package, a `write.vtk` function is provided for such conversion using the command below:

```
write.vtk(points=res[,2:4],lookup_table=rep(1,dim(res)[1]),name='chr21 5kb 3D
structure',opt_path='./chr21_10kb.vtk')
```

Arguments:

points: 3D coordinates predicted by FLAMINGO in the x,y,z format.

lookup_table: The annotation of each point, could be labels or scores, i.e. the compartment PC scores.

name: output file name annotated within the file.

opt_path: output file path including the file name.

Step-by-step Instruction

Here we shown an example of reconstructing the single-cell 3D chromosome structures.

```
tFlamingorLite::tflamingo.data_prepare(code_path, input_folder, low_res, high_res,
outputs_folder, chr_name, assembly)
```

Applies tensor-completion method

```
python Tensor-FLAMINGO/src/Paralized_Low_rank_tensor_completion_FFTW.py -i
'./lowres_contact_maps_transformed' -o './LRTC_low_res_contact_maps' -s low_resolution
-max_iter 150 -n_core 10
python Tensor-FLAMINGO/src/Paralized_Low_rank_tensor_completion_FFTW.py -i
'./highres_contact_maps_transformed' -o './LRTC_high_res_contact_maps' -s
high_resolution -max_iter 150 -n_core 10
python Tensor-FLAMINGO/src/Extract_matrix_from_LRTC.py -i
'./LRTC_low_res_contact_maps/low_resolution.npy' -o './low_res_contact_maps_FLAMINGO'
python Tensor-FLAMINGO/src/Extract_matrix_from_LRTC.py -i
'./LRTC_high_res_contact_maps/high_resolution.npy' -o
'./high_res_contact_maps_FLAMINGO'
```

Reconstruct the 3D chromatin structures:

```
library(tFlamingorLite)
n = length(dir(paste0(outputs_folder,'/high_res_contact_maps_FLAMINGO')))/2
```

```

res_list <- list()
if(dir.exists(paste0(outputs_folder,"Tensor-FLAMINGO_results"))){
  print('results dir already exist')
}else{
  dir.create(paste0(outputs_folder,"/Tensor-FLAMINGO_results"))
}
for (idx in 1:n) {
  input_PD_high =
paste0(outputs_folder,"/high_res_contact_maps_FLAMINGO/PD_Cell_",idx,".txt")
  input_IF_high =
paste0(outputs_folder,"/high_res_contact_maps_FLAMINGO/IF_Cell_",idx,".txt")
  input_PD_low =
paste0(outputs_folder,"/low_res_contact_maps_FLAMINGO/PD_Cell_",idx,".txt")
  input_IF_low =
paste0(outputs_folder,"/low_res_contact_maps_FLAMINGO/IF_Cell_",idx,".txt")

  res_list[[idx]] <- tFlamingoLite::tflamingo.main_func(outputs_folder,
                                                    idx,input_PD_high,
                                                    input_IF_high,
                                                    input_PD_low,
                                                    input_IF_low,
                                                    domain_res=low_res,
                                                    frag_res = high_res,
                                                    chr_name = chr_name,
                                                    nThread = 20,
                                                    sample_rate = 0.75,
                                                    lambda = 10,
                                                    max_dist = 0.01,
                                                    error_threshold = 1e-3,
                                                    max_iter = 500)

  write.table(res_list[[idx]], file = paste0(outputs_folder,"/Tensor-
FLAMINGO_results/Cell_",idx,".txt"), sep = "\t", col.names = TRUE, row.names = FALSE)
}

```